

**EFFICIENCY OF USING PURCAS AGGREGATES IN CHEMIZING
INTENSIVE PARKS AND PEST TOXORS**

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Annotation. The article details the current state and significance of using magenta aggregates with dense volumes for chemically intensive parks and currents.

Key words. intensive fleet, purcar units, innovation, innovation activities, equipment, technologies, modernization, innovation-technical, potential, resource-intensive.

As in all spheres of the republic's economy, serious reforms are being carried out in agriculture. Today, the gardening industry also occupies an important place in agriculture. One of the urgent problems of today is the accelerated development of the horticultural industry, the increase in production volumes using modern and innovative technologies in the industry, as well as the uninterrupted provision of the population with high-quality and affordable products of domestic production.

In this regard, in recent years, the state has been implementing many measures. In particular, DP-5853-son Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020 - 2030 "of October 23, 2019, Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of March 20, 2019" On PD -4246-son measures for the further development of gardening and greenhouse farming in the Republic of Uzbekistan, "in PD -3117-son of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of July 7, 2017 adopted decisions" On measures for the further development of the scientific and technical base of mechanical engineering in agriculture."

Based on these solutions, measures are being taken to develop innovative projects in agriculture, effectively use scientific and technical innovations, and create and stimulate an innovative material and technical base.

Of course, of particular importance for effectively solving these problems and obtaining high yields in gardening is the role of small purple aggregates for intensive parks and vineyards.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. According to (FAO), every year plant diseases cause enormous damage to the global economy, the

main problem of purple remedies in chemical treatment against pests and plant diseases is insufficient treatment of pest habitats on plants, including the main element in purkash aggregates - median mass diameter and dispersion of vessels formed with salts do not fully meet agrotechnical requirements

According to the calculations of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, 20 to 40 percent of agricultural products are lost annually under the influence of pests. Every year, plant diseases damage the global economy by nearly US \$220 billion and invasive insects by US \$70 billion.

One of the urgent issues today is the organization of the use and use of purple aggregates with dense volumes for the chemization of intensive parks and pest currents. The use of purkar aggregates with dense volumes for the chemicalization of intensive parks and vineyards ensures a high level of development of this industry in Uzbekistan.

To this end, the quality of protection of intensive parks and vineyards from diseases and pests will now be improved by the development of small-sized purkash aggregates for intensive parks and vineyards and the consumption of chemical funds will be prevented.

Depending on the goal above, the implementation of the following tasks is unprofitable.

1. Analysis of the current state and development prospects of intensive protection of parks and vineyards against diseases and pests;
2. Conducting theoretical studies to substantiate the parameters and develop a design diagram of the working elements of a small-sized purkash unit;
3. Experimental justification of operating modes of the small-sized purkach unit depending on the growing periods of intensive parks and currents, the rate of consumption of working fluid;
4. Development of basic requirements for the design of small purple units;
5. Conducting laboratory and field studies to justify the parameters of the small purple unit;
6. Determination of technical, environmental and economic indicators of the developed small purple unit;

It can be concluded that in the case of the development, substantiation and introduction of small-sized purkach aggregates for intensive parks and vineyards, which will increase the quality of protection of intensive parks and vineyards from diseases and pests, prevents waste of chemical means and with environmentally friendly innovative chemical protection technology, the following results will be achieved and achieved

1. Analysis of existing structures and application of small-size purcar aggregates, as well as results of theoretical studies on substantiation of parameters and design scheme of small-size purcar aggregates make it possible to identify economic and environmental disadvantages. When creating, introducing into production and using small purple aggregates, losses of chemical agent in soil and atmosphere are obtained from 30% to 50%.
2. The dynamics of the efficiency of intensive parks and currents for 1 using small-sized purkar aggregates has been determined, which will make it possible to effectively use chemical agents and justify much more environmentally friendly innovative technologies.

References:

1. DP-5853-son Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of October 23, 2019 "On the approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030."
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of March 20, 2019 "On measures for the further development of gardening and greenhouse farming in the Republic of PD -4246-sleep."
3. H. D. Irisov S. Results of the study of an experimental purkach unit equipped with a turbulizer saltwater//Journal "Irrigation and Reclamation" No. 4 (18) of 2019.